

Combined *in-situ* microscopy and acoustic emission monitoring of transverse cracking in CFRP cross-ply laminates

S. Spyridonidis^{1,*}, G. Allegri¹, T. Laux¹, and N. Chandarana¹

¹Bristol Composites Institute, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK

[*spyros.spyridonidis@bristol.ac.uk](mailto:spyros.spyridonidis@bristol.ac.uk)

bristol.ac.uk/composites

EPSRC Centre for Doctoral
Training in Composites Science,
Engineering and Manufacturing

Presentation outline

- Transverse matrix cracking in cross-ply laminates
- Experimental setup
- Results
- Conclusions and outlook

Transverse Cracking

Transverse Cracks schematic (1)

- The first damage mode under most of the thermomechanical loading cases
 - Immediate sequencies in thermomechanical properties and precursor for further damage types.

Aim

Experimentally observation of the damage evolution using in-situ microscopy and acoustic emission under quasi-static loading

Specimen

- Tensile specimens from IM7/8552 according to ASTM D3039 Standard
- Two cross ply configurations
- Preparation for testing : Polished edge and DIC speckling

$[0_2/90_6/0]_s$

$[0_3/90_6]_s$

Specimen

Experimental set-up

Image Processing for crack detection ⁷

Results (1)

- Rapid crack increase for both lay-ups configurations
- Thin plies accumulate larger number of cracks/mm
- Both layups steep crack increase
- For blocked case the load for crack initiation is decreased
- Stochasticity of the phenomenon

Combined *in-situ* microscopy and acoustic emission of transverse cracking in CFRP cross-ply laminates

Results (2)

Along with the formation of straight cracks, in both configurations it was observed:

- Oblique cracks
- C-shaped cracks

$[0_2/90_6/0]_s$

Load 20.8kN

$[0_3/90_6]_s$

Load 17.6kN

Results (2)

Along with the formation of straight cracks, in both configurations it was observed:

- Oblique cracks
- C-shaped cracks

$[0_2/90_6/0]_s$

Load 24.4kN
(Failure Load 27.8kN)

$[0_3/90_6]_s$

Load 21kN
(Failure Load 28.7kN)

Results (3)

$[0_2/90_6/0]_S$

Correlation between the two experimental methods

The peak frequency of the AE hits are found in a range of 50-200kHz

Combined *in-situ* microscopy and acoustic emission of transverse cracking in CFRP cross-ply laminates

Conclusions and Outlook

Conclusions

- Oblique, and c-shaped cracks were observed along the formation of straight cracks, without necessary interaction of other cracks.
- The nature of nature of matrix cracking is stochastic not only in terms of spatial distribution but also regarding the number of cracks
- Matrix cracking initiation and progression was captured from both experimental techniques, using microscopy data to validate acoustic emission data

Future Work

Acoustic Emission:

- Implement a classifier with the labeled acoustic emission data from matrix cracking

Microscopy

- Training the crack detection model with a wider dataset to increase the accuracy
- Check the sensitivity of the set-up, with quasi-isotropic layup configuration.

Combined *in-situ* microscopy and acoustic emission of transverse cracking in CFRP cross-ply laminates

Thank you for your attention!
Any questions?

Combined in-situ microscopy and acoustic emission monitoring of transverse cracking in CFRP cross-ply laminates

S. Spyridonidis^{1,*}, G. Allegri¹, T. Laux¹, and N. Chandarana¹

¹Bristol Composites Institute, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK

[*spyros.spyridonidis@bristol.ac.uk](mailto:spyros.spyridonidis@bristol.ac.uk)

**Bristol
Composites
Institute**

bristol.ac.uk/composites